

MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING, COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY AND USAGE IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF GYNECOLOGICAL MALIGNANT NEOR GENERATIONS

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Introduction: *In the structure of total mortality, the second place after diseases of the cardiovascular system is occupied by mortality from malignant neoplasms (MNT). Often, newly diagnosed oncological diseases have a common stage and require expensive treatment, sometimes with permanent disability. This dictates the need for more active implementation of screening programs.*

Purpose: *Evaluation of the prevalence of malignant neoplasms according to magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT) and ultrasound diagnostics (ultrasound).*

Materials and Methods: We analyzed the results of 400 MRI, CT and ultrasound examinations performed on the basis of the 1-clinic of the SamSMU, conducted from 01.2019 to 02.2022. 255 patients with an established diagnosis of MN were examined as part of a comprehensive diagnosis. In 232 patients, it was possible to assess the prevalence of the process by two or more methods, which are included in this analysis. Some patients underwent subsequent intraoperative evaluation (45%). A total of 120 patients with cervical carcinoma, 63 with ovarian carcinoma, 54 with endometrial carcinoma, 43 with breast carcinoma, and 6 patients with vulvar carcinoma were examined.

Results: The greatest accuracy in determining the size of the cervical tumor and parametric invasion was shown by MRI with a sensitivity of 70% and specificity of 89%, ultrasound - 60% and 75%, and CT - 50 and 69%, respectively. For the diagnosis of lymphogenous metastases in cervical cancer, the sensitivity of MRI was 49.8% for CT 42%. MRI was the most accurate in detecting tumor invasion into the myometrium and endometrium with a sensitivity of 75% and a specificity of 88.5%. CT, MRI and ultrasound showed equally high accuracy in the differential diagnosis of benign ovarian tumors, with an accuracy of up to 94%. The greatest difficulty was represented by formations with minimal stromal

invasion regardless of location due to the absence of clear visualized signs of tumor growth.

Conclusions: The diagnostic capabilities of MRI, CT and ultrasound are important diagnostic methods in oncogynecological practice and are widely used for pretreatment staging. Knowing the strengths and weaknesses of each method and their correct combination allows the most accurate assessment of the prevalence of the process, which is very important for choosing an adequate treatment program.